

United Circles implements a partnership of 44 partners across 16 countries & 1 UN body to connect to the H4C EU CoP and to EU & global circularity, process industry & decarbonisation networks.

The main objective of United Circles is to accelerate our progress to a fully decarbonised future without waste and with closed water loops.

By fostering a problem-solving circularity culture, we address urban waste at its source and across process industries.

In United Circles, three value chain demonstrators will each be integrated into a Hub 4 Circularity that will underpin their Industrial-Urban networks governance and evolution, using advanced governance frameworks, feasibility towards financing methodologies, digital tools, social and environmental innovations, and a material and products observatory.

HUBS

SALAMANCA HUB | Urban Waste Water (UWW)

Advance the Water-Energy-Resource nexus towards optimal secondary raw material recovery, improved energy efficiency and closed water loops, fostering the implementation of a circular economy at regional scale

ANKARA HUB | Urban Construction & Demolition Waste (C&DW)

Ankara H4C Technology Innovation Ecosystem: Industry Urban Symbiosis for C&DW Upcycling in Construction Value Chain

VENETO HUB | Urban Food Waste - Used Cooking Oil (UCO)

Transforming used cooking oils into bioplastics and bio-based materials: advanced biorefining and urban-industrial symbiosis, developing products relevant to urban environments and agriculture

MIRRORING HUBS

Each of the Demonstrator H4C will be followed by four Mirroring Hubs for replication

EASTERN MACEDONIA & THRACE HUB

SOUTHERN TRANSDANUBIA HUB

GAUTENG HUB

KENT, EAST AND WEST SUSSEX AND BRIGHTON & HOVE HUB

SEED HUBS

The concept of 'Seed Hubs' for H4C will be tested by four beneficiaries

VELENJE HUB

BEIRUT HUB

NOUVELLE-AQUITAINE HUB

GRAZ HUB

<https://unitedcircles.eu/>

